

Measurement of anomalous magnetic moment of τ lepton at CMS

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Abstract

Measurements of the lepton anomalous magnetic moment provide one of the most stringent tests of the Standard Model (SM) and a sensitive probe for physics Beyond the Standard Model (BSM). The anomalous magnetic moment of the tau lepton (a_τ) can be studied through ditau production via photon-fusion processes involving two $\gamma\tau\tau$ vertices. The CMS Collaboration has recently measured a_τ using two collision systems characterized by distinct ditau invariant-mass regions. The CMS measurement in proton proton (pp) collisions sets a limit on a_τ that is five times more stringent than the previous best constraint from DELPHI, which had stood for over two decades. Meanwhile, the measurement of the ditau production cross section in PbPb collisions exhibits significantly smaller uncertainties compared to pp, highlighting the complementarity of the two systems.

1 Introduction

The Dirac equation predicts a lepton magnetic moment of $g = 2$, but quantum loop effects make it slightly larger, with the leading QED contribution given by the Schwinger term $a = (g - 2)/2 = \alpha/(2\pi)$. Precision measurements of lepton magnetic moments provide stringent tests of the Standard Model (SM) and powerful probes of physics Beyond the Standard Model (BSM). The electron anomalous magnetic moment a_e , measured to ten significant figures [1], stands among the most precise experimental tests of the SM.

However, the short lifetime of the τ lepton prevents a direct determination of its magnetic moment through spin precession, so a_τ must be probed indirectly via the $\gamma\tau\tau$ vertex. The strongest constraint was set by DELPHI using photon-induced ditau production in e^+e^- collisions. More recently, the LHC experiments have opened new avenues to study a_τ through the process $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$. In 2023, CMS [2] and ATLAS [3] observed this process in Ultraperipheral Collisions (UPC) in PbPb for the first time, enabling improved constraints on a_τ . CMS subsequently updated the measurement using the full 2018 PbPb dataset with increased luminosity and additional decay channels [4].

CMS has also observed $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ in proton proton (pp) collisions for the first time [5], providing the most stringent constraints on a_τ to date. Using an effective field theory approach, the analysis also constrains the τ electric dipole moment (d_τ), which is negligibly small in the SM but can be enhanced by new physics.

Two complementary collision systems are therefore exploited by the CMS experiment [6]: (i) UPCs in PbPb, where the $\gamma\gamma$ flux is enhanced by the factor Z^4 (with Z the atomic number of lead), and (ii) pp collisions, which provide access to higher invariant masses where potential BSM effects on a_τ are amplified. This proceeding presents a summary of the latest CMS results in both systems.

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2 $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau\tau$ in PbPb UPCs

UPCs occur when two Pb nuclei pass with an impact parameter exceeding twice the nuclear radius, effectively suppressing hadronic interactions. In this regime, the interaction is dominated by coherent electromagnetic fields, resulting in a final state with very low track multiplicity, negligible pileup, and minimal nonexclusive backgrounds. The large nuclear charge of lead ($Z = 82$) produces an intense flux of quasireal photons, with the $\gamma\gamma$ production rate scaling as Z^4 . This substantial enhancement makes PbPb UPCs a powerful environment for studying photon–photon fusion processes.

The first CMS analysis of $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ in PbPb collisions uses the 2015 dataset collected at a nucleon–nucleon center-of-mass energy of $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 5.02$ TeV, corresponding to an integrated luminosity of $404 \mu\text{b}^{-1}$. By exploiting the dependence of the total $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ cross section on the anomalous magnetic moment, the measurement provides the first LHC constraint on a_τ : $(-8.8 < a_\tau < 5.6) \times 10^{-2}$ (68% Confidence Level (CL)).

More recently, CMS has updated this measurement using up to 1.70 nb^{-1} of PbPb data collected in 2018. The analysis benefits from a fourfold increase in integrated luminosity, the inclusion of three additional $\tau\tau$ decay channels, and the use of both fiducial cross sections and differential kinematic distributions to extract a_τ . A detailed description follows:

2.1 Analysis strategy and results

In PbPb UPCs, the lead nuclei scatter or dissociate in the very forward direction, resulting in low activity in the hadronic forward (HF) calorimeters. The $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ signal therefore has a very clean signature of two oppositely charged τ leptons that are nearly back-to-back in the transverse plane (i.e. $A = 1 - |\Delta\phi|/\pi < 0.1$, where A denotes the acoplanarity). The analysis targets the $\mu + 1prong$, $\mu + 3prong$, $e + 3prong$ and $\mu + e$ decay channels.

Signal samples of the process $\text{PbPb} \rightarrow \text{Pb}^{(*)}(\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-)\text{Pb}^{(*)}$ are generated with the UPCGEN generator [7], which allow to compute ditau cross sections for arbitrary values of a_τ . Photonuclear backgrounds are suppressed using a data-driven ABCD method, while exclusive $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \mu\mu(\gamma)$ and $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow ee$ backgrounds are modeled with simulation. Both the fiducial cross section of the signal process and the kinematics of the visible tau decay products depend a_τ . The analysis extracts a_τ by performing a simultaneous fit to the lepton transverse momentum distributions in the four reconstructed decay channels, such as muon p_T for the three channels with muon and electron p_T for $e + 3prong$ channel, see Fig. 1. The fit is performed in the fiducial phase space defined by τ lepton $p_T > 1$ GeV and $|\eta| < 3$.

Figure 1: Postfit lepton p_T distributions for the $\mu+1prong$ (left) and $e+3prong$ (right) channels. The $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau\tau$ signal shown in light-green is stacked on the background. From Ref. [4].

The signal templates are generated for 21 discrete values in the range $-0.1 < a_\tau < 0.1$, then smoothed and morphed to provide finer granularity. For each a_τ point, the negative log-likelihood of the fit to data is evaluated, allowing systematic uncertainties to vary within their constraints. The resulting two-dimensional likelihood map, shown in Fig. 2, displays the 1σ and 2σ confidence contours in the (a_τ, σ) plane. The black dashed illustrates the expected relation between the cross section and a_τ , obtained from UPCGEN and normalized to the measured cross section at $a_\tau = 0$. The variation of the likelihood along this curve, displayed in Fig. 2 (right) is used to determine the final limits on both a_τ and $\sigma(\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau\tau)$.

Figure 2: Left: Simultaneous limits on the $\sigma(\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau\tau)$ and a_τ . Right: Observed negative log-likelihood as a function of a_τ , for the combined four decay channels. From Ref. [4].

A likelihood fit to the lepton transverse-momentum distributions yields a fiducial cross section of $\sigma(\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-) = 447_{-11}^{+16} \mu\text{b}$ (68% CL), representing the most precise measurement to date, and constrains the anomalous magnetic moment to $-0.045 < a_\tau < -0.017$ (68% CL) and $-0.055 < a_\tau < 0.017$ (95% CL). This corresponds to more than a fourfold improvement over the previous CMS PbPb result and achieves a precision comparable to that of ATLAS and DELPHI.

3 $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau\tau$ in pp collisions

The measurement in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV during Run 2 provides a complementary probe of the tau anomalous magnetic moment. Unlike PbPb, pp interactions lack flux enhancement and have higher backgrounds, but benefit from a large integrated luminosity of 138 fb^{-1} and access a higher ditau mass range ($50 < m_{\tau\tau} < 500$ GeV), where BSM effects on a_τ are enhanced.

3.1 Analysis Strategy and results

The pp analysis also targets four final states: $e\mu, e\tau_h, \mu\tau_h$ and $\tau_h\tau_h$, where τ_h denotes hadronic tau decay. Similar to UPC, the Photon-induced ditau in pp are required to exhibit: a back-to-back topology ($A < 0.015$) and low track multiplicity N_{tracks} (0 or 1 track near the vertex).

Signal samples of elastic $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ are generated using the GAMMA-UPC generator [8]. Nonelastic contributions, in which at least one proton fragments, are not included in GAMMA-UPC and are instead estimated from the $\mu\mu$ final state. The $\mu\mu$ sample is also used to derive corrections for Acoplanarity, pileup and hard scattering track multiplicity.

While PbPb analyses use form factors to extract a_τ , the pp analysis employs a SMEFT framework to extract both a_τ and d_τ , which reduces to the form factor formalism in the limit of

zero momentum transfer ($q^2 = 0$). The $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau\tau$ signal and the corresponding constraints on a_τ and d_τ are then obtained by fitting the signal shape and normalization to the visible invariant mass of the ditau system m_{vis} , see Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Left: Invariant mass of the visible system in $\mu\tau h$ final state with $N_{\text{tracks}} = 0$, with the $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau\tau$ signal shown in red. Right: Expected and observed negative log-likelihood as a function of a_τ , for the combination of all SRs. From Ref. [5].

CMS has observed the $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ process in pp collisions for the first time with a significance of 5.3σ . From this measurement, the anomalous magnetic moment of the tau lepton is constrained to $-0.0042 < a_\tau < 0.0062$ (95% CL), and the tau electric dipole moment is limited to $|d_\tau| < 2.9 \times 10^{-17} e \text{ cm}$ (95% CL). These results represent the world's most stringent constraints on a_τ to date.

The pp and PbPb measurements probe different regimes and offer complementary sensitivities:

Feature	PbPb UPCs	pp Collisions
Photon flux	Very large (Z^4)	Small
Backgrounds	Very low	Significant
$m_{\tau\tau}$ range	$< 40 \text{ GeV}$	Up to 500 GeV
Strength	Precise cross section	Best limits on a_τ
a_τ (95% CL)	$-0.055 < a_\tau < 0.017$	$-0.0042 < a_\tau < 0.0062$

Table 1: Comparison of the main features of PbPb UPC and pp measurements at CMS.

4 Summary

CMS has measured photon-induced $\tau^+\tau^-$ production in both PbPb and pp collisions with unprecedented precision. The PbPb analysis yields the most precise cross section measurement and improves the a_τ sensitivity by a factor of four, while the pp measurement achieves the first observation of $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau\tau$ in pp collisions and sets the world's most stringent limits on a_τ . These complementary measurements significantly advance our understanding of tau electromagnetic properties and offer important probes of physics BSM.

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